

Fracture Mechanics for Delamination Problems in Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

A fracture mechanics approach to the well-known delamination problem in composite materials is presented. Based on the theory of anisotropic laminate elasticity and interface fracture mechanics concepts, the composite delamination problem is formulated and solved. The exact order of the delamination crack-tip stress singularity is determined. Asymptotic stress and displacement fields for an interlaminar crack are obtained. Fracture mechanics parameters such as mixed-mode stress intensity factors, K_I , K_{II} , K_{III} , and the energy release rate, G , for composite delamination problems are defined. For illustration, numerical solutions for delaminated graphite-epoxy composites under uniform axial extension are presented. Effects of fiber orientation, ply thickness, and delamination length on the interlaminar fracture behavior are examined.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination, sometimes also called interlaminar cracking, is one of the frequently encountered types of damage in advanced composite materials. The problem is not only of great theoretical interest but also of significant technical importance. The presence and growth of delamination cracks in composite laminates may lead to severe reliability and safety problems, such as the reduction of structural stiffness, exposure of the interior to adverse environment, and disintegration of the material, which may cause the final failure. Thus understanding the basic mechanics of delamination is of critical importance in the characterization of flaw criticality and assessment of structural integrity of advanced composite materials and structures.

The delamination problem is generally very complex in nature and difficult to solve, because it involves not only geometric and materials discontinuities, but also the inherently coupled, mode I, II and III fracture in an anisotropic, layered material system. This situation is especially true in angle-ply composite laminates, in which delamination is inherently three-dimensional. The composite delamination is basically a fracture problem involving an interlaminar crack between two highly anisotropic, fiber-reinforced laminae. The problem of an interfacial crack between two dissimilar isotropic materials has received much attention recently, for example, Refs. 1-12. But the study of a delamination between strongly anisotropic fiber composites has been very limited, to the author's knowledge. In this paper, a study of the basic nature of the delamination problem in the context of the recently developed interlaminar fracture mechanics for composite laminates is presented.

BASIC ASSUMPTIONS

Consider a composite material (Fig. 1) composed of unidirectional fiber-reinforced plies of uniform thicknesses, h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n . For simplicity and without loss of generality, we restrict ourselves to the cases of symmetric composite laminates with fiber orientations $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots/\theta_2/\theta_1]$ and ply thicknesses, $h_1 = h_n, h_2 = h_{n-1}, \dots$. The composite has a width $2b$ and is subjected to a uniform axial extension, e , along the z axis. The composite laminate is sufficiently long that, in the region far away from the ends, end effects are negligible by virtue of Saint Venant's principle. Consequently, stresses in the composite are independent of the z axis. Delamination occurs in the form of an interlaminar crack between dissimilar plies with fiber orientations, θ_k and θ_{k+1} . Perfect bonding is assumed in the composite everywhere except the region of delamination.

GOVERNING DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND GENERAL SOLUTIONS

A general theory for the mechanics of delamination fracture in composite materials has been developed recently by the author, and some of the preliminary results were reported in (13,14). Due to space limitation, only a brief outline of the theory is given here; detailed mathematical derivation, solution accuracy and convergence, and further interlaminar fracture mechanics interpretations are given in (13-15). It is only stated that formulation of the delamination problem is based on the theory of anisotropic laminate elasticity and that well-known Lekhnitskii's stress functions (16) are used to establish governing partial differential equations. An eigenfunction expansion method is employed for determining the stress singularity at the delamination crack tip. The boundary collocation technique is then used to evaluate the complete solution for finite-dimensional composite laminates having delamination cracks under mechanical loading.

Governing Partial Differential Equations

For each individual fiber-reinforced lamina with rectilinear anisotropy of a general form, the constitutive equations may be expressed by the generalized Hooke's law in contracted notation as

$$\epsilon_i = S_{ij} \sigma_j \quad (i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6), \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_i and σ_j are strain and stress components, and S_{ij} , the compliance tensor, respectively. The engineering strains, ϵ_i , are defined in a Cartesian coordinate system by $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_x, \epsilon_2 = \epsilon_y, \dots, \epsilon_5 = 2\epsilon_{xz}, \epsilon_6 = 2\epsilon_{xy}$, and the stresses σ_i are defined in an analogous manner.

Introducing Lekhnitskii's stress potentials, $F(x, y)$ and $\Psi(x, y)$, and following the procedure given in Ref. 13, one can obtain a pair of coupled, governing partial differential equations as

$$\begin{cases} L_4 F + L_3 \Psi = 0, & (2a) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} L_3 F + L_2 \Psi = 0, & (2b) \end{cases}$$

where L_2, L_3 and L_4 are linear differential operators of the second, third and fourth order, respectively, defined by

$$L_2 = \tilde{S}_{44} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - 2\tilde{S}_{45} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} + \tilde{S}_{55} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}, \quad (3a)$$

$$L_3 = -\tilde{S}_{24} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x^3} + (\tilde{S}_{25} + \tilde{S}_{46}) \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x^2 \partial y} - (\tilde{S}_{14} + \tilde{S}_{56}) \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x \partial y^2} + \tilde{S}_{15} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial y^3}, \quad (3b)$$

$$L_4 = \tilde{S}_{22} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} - 2\tilde{S}_{26} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^3 \partial y} + (2\tilde{S}_{12} + \tilde{S}_{66}) \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} - 2\tilde{S}_{16} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x \partial y^3} + \tilde{S}_{11} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial y^4}, \quad (3c)$$

in which \tilde{S}_{ij} are the reduced compliance tensor defined as

$$\tilde{S}_{ij} = S_{ij} - S_{3i} S_{3j} / S_{33} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 4, 5, 6). \quad (3d)$$

General Solutions for Stresses and Displacements

The governing equations, Eqs. 2a and 2b, are coupled, linear partial differential equations with constant coefficients related to elastic constants of each fiber-reinforced lamina. Wang, et al (13) have shown that, by introducing proper forms for the Lekhnitskii complex stress functions, the general solution for the problem can be expressed as

$$\sigma_x = \sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k \mu_k^2 Z_k^\delta + C_{k+3} \mu_k \bar{Z}_k^\delta] + \sigma_{x0}, \quad \sigma_y = \sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k Z_k^\delta + C_{k+3} \bar{Z}_k^\delta] + \sigma_{y0}, \quad (4a, b)$$

$$\tau_{yz} = -\sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k \eta_k Z_k^\delta + C_{k+3} \bar{\eta}_k \bar{Z}_k^\delta] + \tau_{yz0}, \quad \tau_{xz} = \sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k \mu_k \eta_k Z_k^\delta + C_{k+3} \bar{\mu}_k \bar{\eta}_k \bar{Z}_k^\delta] + \tau_{xzo} \quad (4c, d)$$

$$\tau_{xy} = -\sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k \mu_k Z_k^\delta + C_{k+3} \bar{\mu}_k \bar{Z}_k^\delta] + \tau_{xy0}, \quad (4e)$$

$$u = \sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k p_k Z_k^{\delta+1} + C_{k+3} \bar{p}_k \bar{Z}_k^{\delta+1}] / (\delta+1) + u_0, \quad (5a)$$

$$v = \sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k q_k Z_k^{\delta+1} + C_{k+3} \bar{q}_k \bar{Z}_k^{\delta+1}] / (\delta+1) + v_0, \quad (5b)$$

$$w = \sum_{k=1}^3 [C_k t_k Z_k^{\delta+1} + C_{k+3} \bar{t}_k \bar{Z}_k^{\delta+1}] / (\delta+1) + w_0, \quad (5c)$$

where $Z_k = x + \mu_k y$, and μ_k and η_k are roots of the algebraic characteristic equation given in (13,16). The p_k , q_k and t_k in Eqs. 5a-5c are related to lamina elastic constants and can also be found in Refs. 13 and 16; σ_{i0} , u_{j0} are known quantities determined by using the remote loading conditions for each case studied (13,14). The expression for σ_z can then be obtained as

$$\sigma_z = (e - S_{3j} \sigma_j) / S_{33} \quad (j = 1, 2, 4, 5, 6). \quad (5d)$$

DELAMINATION CRACK-TIP STRESS SINGULARITY

Consider a delamination between the k th and $(k+1)$ th plies in a composite laminate. Assuming that interlaminar crack surfaces are free from traction, one can immediately introduce the following stress boundary conditions:

$$\sigma_y^{(i)} = \tau_{yz}^{(i)} = \tau_{xy}^{(i)} = 0 \quad (i = k, k+1). \quad (6a)$$

The continuity conditions for displacement and interlaminar stress along the ply interface requires

$$\{\sigma_y^{(k)}, \tau_{yz}^{(k)}, \tau_{xy}^{(k)}\} = \{\sigma_y^{(k+1)}, \tau_{yz}^{(k+1)}, \tau_{xy}^{(k+1)}\}, \quad (6b)$$

$$\{u^{(k)}, v^{(k)}, w^{(k)}\} = \{u^{(k+1)}, v^{(k+1)}, w^{(k+1)}\}. \quad (6c)$$

Substituting Eqs. 4a-4e and 5a-5c into the above constraint conditions leads to twelve linear algebraic equations in $C_m^{(k)}$ and $C_m^{(k+1)}$. The nontrivial solution for

$C_m^{(k)}$ and $C_m^{(k+1)}$ requires that the determinant of coefficients of the 12 algebraic equations vanish, i.e.,

$$|\Delta(\delta)|_{12 \times 12} = 0. \quad (6d)$$

This is a standard eigenvalue problem in which δ may be solved from the transcendental equation Eq. 6d, involving material constants, S_{ij} , μ_k , η_k , of plies adjacent to the delamination. The general form of the solution for δ can be written as

$$\delta_n = n \quad \text{or} \quad \delta_n = (n - \frac{1}{2}) \pm i\gamma \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots), \quad (7)$$

where γ is a real constant related to anisotropic elastic constants of fiber-reinforced laminae adjacent to the interlaminar crack only.

Due to the requirement of positive definiteness of strain energy in the elastic composite, the δ_n bounded by

$$-1 < \text{Re}[\delta_n] < 0 \quad (8)$$

characterize the order of the delamination crack-tip stress singularity. For the delaminated $[\pm\theta]_s$ graphite-epoxy composites with various fiber orientations, the eigenvalues δ_n , which satisfy the aforementioned constraint condition, are given in Table 1. The stress singularities for an interlaminar crack between two highly anisotropic laminae are observed to contain a pair of complex conjugates, $\delta_{1,2} = -0.5 \pm i\gamma$, and a constant, $\delta_3 = -0.5$. This situation is unique and different from that of an interface crack between two isotropic or orthotropic media (1-6) in the sense that δ_1 , δ_2 and δ_3 occur simultaneously in the present delamination problem. In the degenerated cases such as $\pm\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° , the composite laminates become unidirectional. The delamination is located in an orthotropic material; thus, the classical inverse square-root singularity for crack-tip stresses is recovered fully.

DELAMINATION STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS IN COMPOSITES

The eigenfunctions in Eqs. 4 and 5 are determined by imposing appropriate materials and geometric symmetry conditions and remote traction boundary conditions. Hence, complete stresses and displacements, σ_i and u_i , in the composite laminate can be fully established. Neglecting the higher-order terms, the general structure of the crack-tip stress field can be shown to have the following form:

$$\sigma_i = \sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 [f_{ijk} z_k^{\delta_j} + g_{ijk} \bar{z}_k^{\delta_j}] \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 6), \quad (9a)$$

where f_{ijk} and g_{ijk} are related to the material constants, geometry, and boundary conditions; δ_j are the eigenvalues bounded by Eq. 8. For the convenience of further developments, the asymptotic stress field around the crack tip is rewritten as

$$\sigma_i = \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_{ij}(x, y; \delta_j) + O(\text{non-singular, higher-order terms}), \quad (9b)$$

where σ_{ij} is the j th component of the singular stress σ_i corresponding to the eigenvalue δ_j which meets Eq. 8.

In view of the stress solution structure given by Eqs. 9a and 9b, it is possible to define in the context of mechanics of fracture the so-called stress intensity factors for the delamination in a manner analogous to that given in Refs. 4-6 by considering the interlaminar stresses, σ_2 , σ_4 and σ_6 (i.e., σ_{11} , τ_{yz} , and τ_{xy}) ahead of the delamination along the ply interface. Thus, one may define

$$K_I = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \sum_{j=1}^3 \sqrt{2\pi} x^{-\delta_j} \sigma_{2j}(x, 0; \delta_j), \quad K_{II} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \sum_{j=1}^3 \sqrt{2\pi} x^{-\delta_j} \sigma_{6j}(x, 0; \delta_j), \quad (10a-b)$$

$$K_{III} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \sum_{j=1}^3 \sqrt{2\pi} x^{-\delta_j} \sigma_{4j}(x, 0; \delta_j). \quad (10c)$$

STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATES FOR DELAMINATION

While the stress intensity factors K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} describe the details of an interlaminar crack-tip field, the strain energy release rate G is also of significant interest, since this is a quantity physically measurable in experiments and mathematically well defined. The fracture energy release rate, G , in a delaminated composite may be evaluated by using Irwin's virtual crack extension concept (17) as

$$\begin{aligned} G &= G_I + G_{II} + G_{III} \\ &= \lim_{\delta\beta \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2\delta\beta} \int_0^{\delta\beta} \{ \sigma_y(r, 0) [v^{(k)}(\delta\beta - r, \pi) - v^{(k+1)}(\delta\beta - r, -\pi)] \\ &\quad + \tau_{xy}(r, 0) [u^{(k)}(\delta\beta - r, \pi) - u^{(k+1)}(\delta\beta - r, -\pi)] \\ &\quad + \tau_{yz}(r, 0) [w^{(k)}(\delta\beta - r, \pi) - w^{(k+1)}(\delta\beta - r, -\pi)] \} dr, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where polar coordinates (r, ϕ) are used for the convenience of computation, and $\delta\beta$ is the length of virtual crack extension. The interlaminar stresses, σ_y , τ_{xy} , and τ_{yz} , in Eq. 11 may be obtained from the crack-tip stress field equations such as Eqs. 4a-4e. The corresponding displacements are also those of the asymptotic field equations obtained in the previous section, i.e., Eqs. 5a-5c.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

For the purpose of illustrating the fundamental nature of the delamination crack behavior in composite materials, graphite-epoxy laminates with symmetric $[\theta/-\theta/-\theta/\theta]$ fiber orientations containing delamination cracks along the θ and $-\theta$ ply interface are studied here. The composite laminate is subjected to a uniform axial extension and has a geometry shown in Fig. 1 with a width-to-thickness ratio $2b/2W$ and uniform ply thickness h_1 . Delamination cracks of length a are assumed to emanate from the edges of the composite. Ply properties typical of high-modulus unidirectional graphite-epoxy composite given in (13,14) are used in the numerical computation.

Influence of Fiber Orientation on Delamination Crack Behavior

Consider the $[\theta/-\theta/-\theta/\theta]$ graphite-epoxy composites with various fiber orientations subjected to uniform axial extension e . For illustration, we choose the composite with a width-to-thickness ratio $2b/(2h)$ equal to 8, ply thickness $h_1 = h_2 = 1$ in., and delamination length $a = 1$ in. The mixed-mode K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} are determined and given in Table 2 for various θ 's. It is observed that even though the composite laminate is under the simplest loading condition, the delamination crack-tip response is very complicated indeed due to the complex interlaminar stress transfer, the nonhomogeneity of the composite, the anisotropy of ply properties, and the unusual delamination configuration with respect to the loading direction. The out-of-plane tearing-mode stress intensity factor K_{III} caused by interlaminar shear τ_{yz} is about one or two orders of magnitude higher than K_I and K_{II} in general in the laminates studied. The opening-mode stress intensity K_I is also very significant due to the significant interlaminar normal stress σ_y . The simultaneous presence of K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} in composite delamination is unique to fiber reinforced laminates, not observed in fracture problems for bonded

dissimilar isotropic media in general. The total energy release rates, G , for the $[\theta/-\theta/-\theta/\theta]$ graphite-epoxy composite laminates with delaminations are shown in Table 3. The results reveal that the energy release rate, i.e., the driving force for delamination, is much higher for a delaminated composite with $\theta \approx 15^\circ$, and has rather small values for $\theta > 45^\circ$, indicating this composite may be more prone to intralaminar cracking than delamination. Obviously, from the present results, the delamination behavior is observed to be inherently three-dimensional in nature. Thus for composites with more general lamination, crack geometry, and loading conditions, fully three-dimensional fracture analyses are essential for obtaining complete information.

Effect of Ply Thickness on Delamination

The effect of laminate geometric variables on the delamination behavior is best illustrated by examining the change of K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} with ply thickness in a $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ]$ graphite-epoxy composite with $h_1 + h_2 = W = 2$ in. Given the delamination crack length ($a = 1$ in.), laminate dimension ($2b = 4$ in.), and the loading condition as before, the delamination stress intensity factors for various h_1/h_2 's cases are obtained in Fig. 2. The crack-tip tearing and opening stresses τ_{yz} and σ_y (or K_{III} and K_I) have maximum intensifications, as the ply thickness h_i become identical, i.e., $h_1/h_2 = 1$. The K_{II} , however, reaches a minimum due to the reduction in τ_{xy} . It should be noted here that the K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} depend on material constants of all plies as well as the overall laminate geometry. Therefore, values of K_i depend not only on ply properties but also on lamination and geometric variables as well as the loading condition.

The delamination strain energy release rate is also a function of the ply thickness. In the $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ]$ graphite-epoxy composite with a geometry given before, the change of G with h_1/h_2 is shown in Fig. 3, where maximum driving force occurs at $h_1 = h_2$, indicating the criticality of the relative ply thickness for delamination fracture in composites.

Interlaminar Crack Length vs Delamination Energy Release Rate

To illustrate the basic nature of delamination extension in laminated composites, strain energy release rates in the $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ]$ graphite-epoxy with various interlaminar crack lengths are presented. Effects of laminate width on delamination crack extension is also investigated. The change of total strain energy release rate G with delamination length a is given in Fig. 4 to illustrate fundamental characteristics of the delamination fracture. For the composite laminates with various $2b/2h$'s, the G is observed to change with delamination length in a unique manner. The energy release rate (or crack extension driving force) reaches a maximum or a relative constant at a length approximately equal to one or two ply thicknesses in the composite studied, depending on the $(2b/2h)$ ratio. As the delamination exceeds this characteristic dimension a^* G decreases monotonically.

From a fracture mechanics perspective, several important features regarding the basic nature of composite delamination are revealed. Assuming that the material resistance to delamination growth remains constant (i.e., the failure criterion, $G_c = \text{constant}$, is used), one may find that there exists a critical delamination length associated with the maximum G for each composite laminate (for example, $a^* \approx 2h$ for the case $b/h = 8$); the word "critical" means that the one that experiences unstable crack extension at the lowest load. It also indicates that any inherent interlaminar flaw a_0 in the composite, which is less than a^* , will experience rapidly unstable growth as the load or G reaches a critical level, and is anticipated to be arrested at a later stage. Any initial delamination greater than a^* will experience a stable growth under a monotonically rising load. Thus there may exist an inherently built-in crack arrest mechanism for the delamination. The phenomena explained by the $G - a$ curve have been noted by several researchers conducting experimental and analytical studies on the delamination fracture. The a^* may be an important quantity in the life prediction for delaminated composite materials and structures subjected to static and cyclic loading.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on the information given in the paper, the following remarks may be suggested:

1. The proposed analytical method based on the theory of anisotropic elasticity may be successfully used to study delamination problems in composite laminates. Formulation of the problem is carried out by using Lekhnitskii's complex variable stress functions.
2. Stress singularities for a delamination crack between highly anisotropic laminae are obtainable by using an eigenfunction analysis. The order of delamination crack-tip stress singularity is different from that of an interface crack between dissimilar isotropic or orthotropic media by the simultaneous presence of three characteristic eigenvalues of $-0.5+i\gamma$, and $-0.5-i\gamma$, and -0.5 .
3. The fracture mechanics concept may be extended to delamination problems in anisotropic composite laminates by properly defining the interlaminar crack-tip stress intensity factors and strain energy release rates. For delaminated angle-ply composite laminates, K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} always occur simultaneously with K_{III} being one or two orders of magnitude higher than the other two.
4. The crack extension driving force or strain energy release rate for delamination in composite laminates can be accurately determined by using Irwin's virtual crack extension concept. Delamination stability in composite laminates may be assessed for any inherent interlaminar flaw relative to the critical delamination size a^* obtained in the $G - a$ curve.
5. Fiber orientation, ply thickness, stacking sequence and related lamination variables are found to influence the delamination crack behavior (in terms of K_I , K_{II} , K_{III} , and G) significantly.

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TABLE 1

Dominant Stress Singularities for Delamination in $[\theta/-\theta/-\theta/\theta]$ Graphite-Epoxy Composites

θ	$\delta_{1,2}$	δ_3
0°	-0.5	-0.5
15°	-0.5 ± 0.00642i	-0.5
30°	-0.5 ± 0.02399i	-0.5
45°	-0.5 ± 0.03434i	-0.5
60°	-0.5 ± 0.02942i	-0.5
75°	-0.5 ± 0.01579i	-0.5
90°	-0.5	-0.5

TABLE 2

Stress Intensity Factors $K_I^{*†}$ for Edge Delamination in $[\theta/-\theta/-\theta/\theta]$ Graphite-Epoxy Composite[‡] Subjected to Uniform Axial Extension, $\epsilon_z = e$.

$\pm\theta$	K_I	K_{II}	K_{III}
15°	0.08645	0.01214	-4.5588
30°	0.23300	0.03330	-3.6604
45°	0.13470	0.01380	-1.2968
60°	0.02025	0.00136	-0.1775
75°	0.00627	-0.00029	0.0818

* K_I (psi - $\sqrt{\text{in.}}$) are scaled by $10^6 e$.

‡ $a = h_1 = h_2 = 1$ in.; $b = 8$ in.

†for the delamination crack in the first quadrant.

TABLE 3

Energy Release Rate G for Edge Delamination in $[\theta/-\theta/-\theta/\theta]$ Graphite-Epoxy Composite[†] under Uniaxial Extension, $\epsilon_z = e$.

$\pm\theta$	$G/10^6 e^2$ (psi-in.)
15°	8.1076
30°	4.0506
45°	0.5740
60°	0.0138
75°	0.0036

† $a = h_1 = h_2 = 1$ in.; $b = 8$ in.

Fig. 1 Coordinates and Geometry of a $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\theta_1/\theta_2]$ Composite Laminate with Delamination under Uniform Axial Extension $\epsilon_z = e$

Fig. 2 Stress Intensity Factors, K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} , of an Edge Delamination Crack in $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ]$ Graphite-Epoxy Composite with Various Ply-Thickness Ratios h_1/h_2

Fig. 3 Effects of Ply Thickness h_1/h_2 on Strain Energy Release Rate G in $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ]$ Graphite-Epoxy Composite ($a = 1$ in., $2b = 4$ in.)

Fig. 4 Delamination Strain Energy Release Rate G in $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ]$ Graphite-Epoxy Composites with Various Delamination Crack Length a and Laminate Widths b